

INTERLOCKING BETWEEN TRADITIONAL CUSTODY AND LEMBAGO OF JAMBI MALAY: STUDY OF MEANING

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Abstract

Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi Malay is one of the traditions in the custom of Malay Jambi marriage. This tradition is a traditional event that has been passed down through generations in the form of Seloko Adat, which is full of the meaning of life that needs to be preserved. Therefore, the aim of the research is expressing the meanings which are contained in it. The method used in this research is qualitative descriptive with content and hermeneutic analysis approach and to obtain the validity of the data used triangulation. The Result of the research are 1. Kato Bajawab in front of the house between the elders or spokesman from the bride and the groom, 2. Continuing to the ballroom, the event is starting with 1) read the Al-Quran, 2) eating betel leaves and smoking cigarettes, 3) the parents of the groom gave something to the bride, 4) the elders of the bride and groom checked and received delivery, 5) the grandmothers of both parties asked for an order or opinion from the mediators, 6) customary procession accepted by all parties, 7) determination of marriage day, 8) prayer reading, and 9) informal conversation. From the results of the research, the meaning contained in seloko Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi can be concluded that Jambi Malays need conformity and harmony which is realized in the form of mutual love, happiness, economy, readiness, responsibility, courtesy, work, tranquility, humility, joy, maintaining good relationships, and living success.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi is part of the tradition in the traditional wedding procession owned by the Jambi Province community that needs to be developed, preserved, and passed down from generation to generation. In the traditional procession, not all skilled people act as actors representing the two parties as the spokesperson, namely the groom and the bride. There are certain people who understand about the stages of tradition that gives something special from the elders of groom side to the bride. The person that knows it clearly in the Jambi Malay tradition is called the elders or spokesperson.

Seloko used by the spokesperson contains various meanings, but not everyone understands the meaning. Most of them only understand as conversation smoothers or as a tradition only [Gafar, 2012]. Syam [2010] in Jambi custom, besides containing various meanings, seloko also contains advice and views of grandmothers, the elders, and clever people for the community. In addition, Gafar [2017] seloko also acts as a norm, philosophy, foundation, and affirmation in conveying the thoughts and feelings of the community and serves as a medium to create an atmosphere that is familiar and contains aesthetic value, a sense of ownership, honor and respect.

In the modern era, the tradition of Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi needs to be preserved and developed. This is because the marriage procession will be more

meaningful if this is done. The financial presence of the groom was also seen in the event. This can be seen from the luggage as a matter of custom, whether carrying a buffalo, a goat, or a chicken or in other terms buffalo-shaped buffalo, not goat-shaped goats or chicken-shaped chickens that have been put in boxes or envelopes.

The ceremony of that tradition in the Jambi Malay community is a very important event for every member of the community. "This sacred ceremony guides new families in the community and between families, and will change the structure of the community with its environment for the presence of new families" [Syam, 2010]. For this reason it must begin with full attention from parents, relatives, and the community so that the marriage is carried out in accordance with the prevailing customs.

2. BASELINE THEORY/MATERIALS/ METHODS

2.1 Baseline Theory

Nukman and Ikhsan [2012] state that seloko was created along with the Jambi Malay tradition with sense and ethics considerations as a social control full of meaning, both associative and lexical meanings. Kempson [1984] lexical meaning is the meaning that appears in the selection of words used by speakers. Leech [1987] has conceptual meaning and associative meaning which is divided into connotative meaning, social meaning, affective meaning, reflective meaning, collocative meaning and thematic meaning. Chaer [1995] states that lexical meaning is the meaning that corresponds to reality that is truly real in life. Whereas, Parera [1991] has interpretive meaning related to the interpretation and response of the reader or listener, writing or speaking, reading or listening. Meanwhile, Kridalaksana [1993] in addition to connotative meanings there are denotative meanings that are straightforward on something outside the language or based on certain conventions.

2.2 Material and Methods

The method used in this study is descriptive qualitative [Arikunto, 2006] with a content analysis and hermeneutic approach [Rohman, 2013]. As well as it is to obtain the validity of the data used techniques namely (1) theory triangulation, (2) methodology triangulation, and (3) expert triangulation. The data source used was Seloko in the marriage video of Fadilatul Hikmah with Alfarabi on February 4, 2017.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Ulur antar serah terimo adat dan lumbago (Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi), was one phase or step three of the eleven stages Jambi Malay traditional wedding procession and is also known by dropping *belanja* (shopping). The procession begins at 1. Kato bajawab in the courtyard between the progenitor or a spokesman for the groom and the bride and 2. Stepping up the ballroom, the event begins with 1) reading the Al-Quran, 2) chewing betel nut and smoking, 3) the elders of the bride handed conduction, 4) the elders of the bride check and receive conduction, 5) both parties have asked edict or opinion of the elders mediator, 6) customary procession received by all the parties, 7) determination of the marriage, 8) reading prayers, and 9) welcoming. Of these stages used *seloko adat*, except on step of reading Al-Qur'an, prayer and welcoming. Among the seloko can be seen along with its meaning as follows.

1. Kato Bajawab in the Yard

The sentence "*Nenek-mamak, tuo tengantai, cerdas pandai, alim ulama*" are conceptually have a meaning elder people, old people, smart people, theologians and by association means institution

of the elders, institutions of smart people, institution of religious people, which has an important role in society that should be respected and appreciated.

The sentence "*Induk-induk yang bersentuk cincin dijari nan bederau gelang di tangan*" conceptually means that the parents (mothers) are wearing a ring on her finger lots and lots of bracelets hand. While the associative meaning mothers who attended the event are the people respected, honorable, beautiful and dignified, as well as those who are economically disadvantaged.

The sentence "*berkain ujung serong, yang bersanggul lipat pandaan*" conceptually means that berkain and bersanggul neatly, while sesara associative means in accordance with customary rules and follow the way of dressing people respectable, neat, harmonious, fragrant and full of happiness.

The sentence "*anak mudo (youngest) capat kaki dan ringan tangan*" conceptually swift-footed meaningful way quickly and handily meaningful hands-down, while in associative swift-footed meaningless without prompting was gone and soft hands without prompting you for helping or doing work with full responsibility in completing the work.

2. Stepping Up the Hill

The sentence "*bukitlah kami daki, lurahlah kami turuni, unaklah kami ateh (potong)*" conceptually means that it is up the hill, already down a ravine, *cut unak* (midrib rattan prickly), whereas in associative means it's real effort despite various obstacles which must be passed to occupy the promise which He swore or to achieve the desired goal with the efforts and hard work.

The sentence "*lah putih mato kami dek memandang, lah ikal pulo rambut di kuduk, nek menengok lah pasak pulo tebing nek meninjau*" conceptually meaningful eyes were white because I have long looked at, hair, curly or frizzy did not get carded, land on the cliff was solid for trampled underfoot, while in associative significant long-awaited concerned does not come repeatedly, causing uncertainty and anxiety for those who wait, but still show calmness.

The sentence "*ibarat orang bepikat ayam lah terdengar kukuknyo, ibarat orang nembaklah tepat nian sasarannyo*" conceptually meaningful voice chicken has been heard and shooting has been on target, while the meaning of associative as person or guest / prospective groom awaited imminent at home prospective bride the woman and the house targeted by a candidate or party bride is not one house or address so that the hearts were dropping and the host was elated.

1) Chewing Betel Nut and Smoking

The sentence "*bukanlah kami nak bauji samo merah, bekati nak samo berat, dak pulo budi nak babalas kasih kan batimbal*" conceptually meaningful not want to test the same red, scales the weight and not return the favor, by association means the host preparing betel Foreword and cigarettes for food, this kind of thing is not for payback but according to the customs and habits of every guest who comes to be fed before asked for what purposes these guests come, this is also done for the courtesy and mutual respect.

The sentence "*kok betemu dengan yang besawar jangan ditempuh, kok betemu dengan yang berebo jangan diungkai*" conceptually means do not pass in a *bersawar* (fencing) and *berebo* (wood in the forest had been cleared but not yet cut) do not *diungkai* (cleaned) whereas the meaning asosiatifnya do not break the rules, etiquette, customs, and cultures, if violated will incur customary law or customs debt as a form of social responsibility.

2) The Elders from the Groom Parties Submitting Conduction

The sentence "*bak kayu gedang ditengah negeri, daunnyo rindang tempat kito beteduh, dahanyo kuat tempat kito begantung, batangnyo gedang tempat kito bersandar, akarnyoko kokoh tepat kito duduk besilo*" conceptually means there was a large wooden in the middle country from another

wood, leaves dense, branches strong hung, the great stem lean, its roots are strong for the seat, while meanings associative symbolize their rulers, or community leaders are very influential for the community to be a place to ask for protection, rescue, and footing both morally and materially or economy in public life.

The sentence "*maklumlah kedatangan kami tadi banyak, lah penuh laman yang ujo, lah mendesak laman yang panjang, rumah nan gedang, mungkin di antaro kami ado yang salah langkah, tangan salah limbai, lidah salah kato*" conceptually meaningful people come a lot, yard extensive is full, long page is already packed, big house, one step, one to work the hand, one speaks, by association means people who come (most of people) find themselves a lot of flaws and errors that are not desired by the host or the parties come which could lead to the wrong place themselves, one by custom or ketersingungan with the words spoken by immigrants the bridegroom to the bride women, it also aims to maintain the propriety and love.

The sentence "*sebagai ulasan jari sambungan tangan, sebagai ulasan kata penyambung lidah*" conceptually means that finger for reviews and hands are connected, said reviews and tongue are connected, but conceptually means that as a messenger of the bridegroom to convey something and as spokesperson to convey the intent and desire of the bridegroom and the bride so well on women as a form of humility.

The sentence "*dimano bumi dipijak, disitu langit di junjung, dimano tembilang dicacak disitu tanaman tumbuh*" conceptually means that Rome, do the Romans, tembilang dicacak and plants grow, by association means someone must conform to the rules of customs, culture, rules that apply everywhere where he was to maintain good relations.

The sentence "*mempunyai anak bujang, itu ibarat harimau di ujung tanjung, dio mengaung kesano, mengaum kesini, tabilo-bilo dio lapar*". "Having girls as the custom is like a fire on a reed, if ado angin blown little burnt" conceptually means that having children flunky like tigers at the tip of the promontory sounded here and there, who knows when he is hungry, has a girl like fire on reed, if the wind a little burned out. By association means that boys have the freedom of roaming around but that freedom must be supervised by their parents not to do that is not good for the girl child. When this happens it will cause havoc and disgrace to the old person on this sigadis especially for older people.

The sentence "*strong wind was the commandment of the timber will be uprooted, aek heavy pounding the cliff, cliffs will crumble*" conceptually means that agin tight timber will fall, cliffs pounded jetted will collapse, by association means that in order to get the desired one must dare to sacrifice anything, Therefore, he must prepare himself properly so as not to drift improper harm himself.

The sentence "*kalu mudik kami lah bagalah, ilir bagalah santang*" conceptually means that going home to put on pole, Iilir to wear satang, by association means to achieve something must be assisted with a variety of equipment and items should be adjusted to its usefulness.

3) The Elders from the Bride Checking And Receiving Gift

The sentence "*kok harilah beganti hari, minggu lah beganti bulan, bahkan bulanlah menjadi tahun*" conceptually means that day by day, weeks turned into months, months turned into years, by association means that the time to wait, wait, and hope that never fulfilled as which are expected.

The sentence "*Kalu jauh mungkin nak kami tinjau. Kok dekat nak kami pegang. Seandainya betali tentu nak kami tarik. Seandainyo kalu betampuk nak kami jinjing*" conceptually means that the conduction brought the men there are distant and some are close. By association means that the conduction delivered the men have not been so apparent to the elders of the bride in this case is examine what is delivered or carried.

The sentence "*nak kami sisik siang dulu nenek mamak, akan kami sisik sampai ke tunggul, lah kami siang sampai ke tunas*" conceptual meaning contained in this Seloko means cleaning gardens to complete a thorough cleansing. While the associative that conduction brought by the groom examined one by one and nothing is left behind.

4) The Elders from Both Parties Asked Edict or Opinion of the Elders of Mediator

The sentence "*Makannyo habis, minumnyo mengering, nyincangnyo memutus, dan menentukan sah dengan batalnyo*" conceptually means that eating should be discharged, drinking should be dry, cutting must break, determine the legitimacy with the cancellation of a work to be done by the elders. By association means all negotiations between the elders from men and women, as well as conduction provided must obtain approval and ratification of the elders arbitrator. They decide the admissibility of such negotiations or conduction.

The sentence "*Kok lebar lah dilipat, kok panjang lah digulung, ado dalam kotak yang sebuah iko*" conceptually means that the folded width, length was coiled, is in the box. By association means that conduction in the form of goods that should have been replaced in another form, namely in the form of money that is described by the sentence fold and roll is already in the box.

The Sentence "*Kami mengharapkan kepada nenek-mamak, kurang yang perlu ditambah, patah yang perlu disisip*" conceptually means that the elders expecting something less needs to be added, broken need to be repair. In associative meaning all talks or less conduction, which needs to be supplemented and corrected in accordance with customary rules. The sentence "*lah banyak laut yang direnaginyo, banyak pulo kampung yang dijelajahinyo, banyak pulo gelangan yang dicubonyo*" conceptually means that the elders's spokesman both sides was a lot of sea to be swum, many village that already explored, and more arena that already tried. By association means that the elders mediator give praise to the elders both sides, that they have a lot of experience about stalling handover between customs and institutions.

The sentence "*titian teras bertanggo batu, dak lekang dek panas, dak lapuk dek hujan*" conceptually means that there is a bridge that is strong made of stone, heat resistance, not weathered by rain. by association means that a household will go well and survive old should be based on honesty, harmony, mutual trust, and resistant to the rumors and slander that struck and need to stay in one direction.

The sentence "*panjang rambut besak sanggulnyo, kalu pendek rambuk kecil sanggulnyo*" conceptually means that if makes a bun in long hair it will be a big bun, if short hair so it will be small bun. by association means that the existence of the economic of men will be seen by their gift. If it is big it means the economic condition of the groom is good and vise versa.

The sentence "*kalu nak tau di luar negeri tanyo dengan burung elang, kalu nak tau dalamnyo aek tanyo dengan berang-berang, kalu nak tau panjangnyo pantai tanyo ikan seluang*" conceptually means that there are hawks clever, there are beavers who know it water, and there are fish that knows the length of the beach, by association means that if you want to ask about something let asked the experts.

The sentence "*Adat di atas tumbuh, lembago di atas tuah*" conceptually means that customary institutions evolve and auspicious, by association significantly when the prospective groom capable of filling custom should not be limited, it is also symbolized by the filling custom, wore two clothes, which are wet and dry. it indicates that it comes ready to provide a living and unseen. As well as the cast institution one buffalo, rice 100 bushels, coconut 100 rope, sweet and salt.

5) The Customary Procession Accepted By All Parties

Poem "*dari Muaro Buat ke Batang Asai, singah berhenti di Dusun Karak, gawe adat sudah selesai, mau dicepat-cepatkan gawe sarak*" Conceptually means that custom work has been

completed and continued work Sarak, by association means faster is better that there should be things that are not desirable and accelerate the good work will be rewarded.

Poem “*dak ado lagi tanah bapingkah, lah ketemu tanah bapayo, dak ado lagi cakap yang batingkah, lah ketemu kato yang seiyo*” conceptually means that the land is no longer cracked, existing brackish soil, speech has been agreed, the words already in one direction. by association means the agreement is complete, custom conduction has been received and all the elders of both parties and the mediator have agreed there is no gap again to debate and accept everything what is negotiated.

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Ulur antar serah terimo adat dan lumbago starting with 1. Kato bajawab in the courtyard between the progenitor or a spokesman for the groom and the bride and 2. Stepping up the ballroom, the event begins with 1) reading the Al-Quran, 2) chewing betel nut and smoking, 3) the elders of the bride handed conduction, 4) the elders of the bride check and receive conduction, 5) both parties have asked edict or opinion of the elders mediator, 6) customary procession received by all the parties, 7) determination of the marriage, 8) reading prayers, and 9) welcoming.

From the stages of these activities are found meaning in the form of love, courage, happiness, economy, happiness, readiness, responsible, well-mannered, jobs, serenity, humility, joy, maintain good relationships, and life success.

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